

EXAMINING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING AND BRAND ENGAGEMENT AMONG PRE-SCHOOL PARENTS IN MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine social media marketing that influences brand engagement among parents of preschoolers' children. The study specifically examines the influences of entertainment, interaction, customization, trendiness, and electronic word of mouth (eWOM) on brand engagement. The research methodology adopted is a quantitative approach and a descriptive cross-sectional research design. The participants of this study were drawn from millennial preschoolers' parents from the District of Petaling, Malaysia. 200 respondents were included in the study via convenience sampling. The measurement was a structured questionnaire that was adopted from previous research. The results revealed that there are two independent variables customization and interaction are having a significant relationship with brand engagement among parents of preschoolers' children. There are three independent variables entertainment, trendiness and electronic word of mouth are not having a significant relationship with brand engagement among parents of preschoolers' children. Pre-schools can be guided by the findings of this study to enhance brand engagement among parents and thus improve their enrollment numbers.

Keywords: social media marketing, brand engagement, entertainment, interaction, customization, trendiness, and electronic word of mouth (eWOM)

INTRODUCTION

Most millennial parents' purchase decisions are influenced by social media as they get their information from them. With this development, social media marketing has become one of the most important ways to reach consumers in Malaysia and around the world (Tjiptono et al., 2020). Harun et al. (2019) posit that millennials get their information from social media which strongly influences their brand engagement. Tjiptono et al. (2020) also state that over 85% of this generation constantly compare products from physical stores and online stores before making purchase decisions. The growth is demonstrated with more than 92% of Malaysians use the internet to search for products and services with millennials being the most adept at this (Digital Business Lab, 2021). Also, more than 8 in 10 Malaysians use social media to assess products through the reviews of other social media users and 7 in 10 reports having made purchases after getting information from social media (Digital Business Lab, 2021). These statistics highlight how brand engagement has changed in Malaysia, particularly among millennials.

According to Harun et al. (2019), this also applies to making decisions on which preschools their children should attend. Other research has also shown that social media platforms play a critical role in preschool selection by parents with many examining the social media presence and reviews and comments of other parents while making a choice for preschool (Hamida et al., 2019). Considering this, it is now more crucial than ever for preschools to have a strong social media presence to attract parents and retain them through brand engagement using social media platforms. For these parents, they must have an understanding of the factors that drive social media brand engagement. Knowledge is essential as they try to navigate the increasingly complex and competitive market for preschool education. This includes elements of entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and electronic word of mouth (eWOM) on brand engagement.

Despite the growing interest and dependability of social media when parents choose preschools, the information on the platform presence of preschools in Malaysia is lacking. In one of the very limited studies to look at the issue, Mustafa et al. (2014) argue that with increasing competition among preschools, social media marketing is one of the most crucial means for private preschools in the country to stand out. The study further emphasized that a strong social media presence designed to drive brand engagement is the next frontier for preschool brands to be prominent. Based on these research findings, it is concluded that social media presence is an increasingly relevant source of information that informs preschool selection among parents. However, there are no past studies that consider social media marketing elements that influence parents' brand engagement for preschools within the District of Petaling, Selangor. The findings will help preschools to leverage social media marketing to increase the level of brand engagement. To address this issue, in this study, the researchers will explore the influences of social media marketing elements on brand engagement for preschool parents. This research study attempts to meet the following questions:

RQ1: Is there a significant relationship between entertainment and brand engagement?

RQ2: Is there a significant relationship between interaction and brand engagement?

RQ3: Is there a significant relationship between trendiness and brand engagement?

RQ4: Is there a significant relationship between customizations and brand engagement?

RQ5: Is there a significant relationship between electronic word (eWOM) of mouth and brand engagement?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social Media Marketing and Brand Engagement

Social media marketing has emerged as one of the most dominant and effective types of digital marketing because the business model of most social media platforms is based on marketing as the basis for income generation. Most social media platforms have built complex algorithms that track and analyze consumer activities for the purposes of marketing (Evans et al., 2021). The effectiveness of social media marketing also stems from the fact that it allows brands, businesses,

and marketers to engage directly with consumers in ways that were not possible before. Businesses can now own brand pages and accounts on social media platforms which allows direct two-way communication that is instantaneous and can happen at any time (Leung et al., 2017). Social media marketing also allows user-generated content such as product reviews to be a core part of the marketing strategy in a more direct way than other forms of marketing. User-generated content also increases brand engagement through social media. Social media marketing has become a dominant and popular form of marketing in Malaysia.

The strategies that underpin social media marketing highlight why it leads to high brand engagement. The strategies are dependent on whether the passive or active approach is taken to social media marketing. Passive marketing is consumer driven and not directly done by the organisation. Product blogs and online customer reviews are important examples of passive marketing. In the passive approach, marketing is largely driven by consumers or organisations that are not directly affiliated with the brand (Evans et al., 2021). In the active approach, the brand directly drives the marketing process with content coming directly from the business or its marketing team. This approach is most evident in brand pages owned by the business itself. Both approaches to social media marketing strategies involve a high level of engagement with the brand or products of the brand.

Brand engagement refers to the creation of an emotional or rational attachment to a brand (Khan et al., 2020). It signifies an emotional commitment to the brand that goes beyond brand awareness. It is critical because it can predict brand loyalty, purchase intention, and the propensity of consumers to spread positive word-of-mouth marketing (Obilo et al., 2021). For some time now, social media marketing has been highly effective because it drives brand engagement more effectively than most other types of marketing. Gómez et al. (2019) note that this is the key purpose of most social media marketing campaigns. It drives brand engagement primarily because customers and stakeholders are active participants rather than passive viewers as is the case for most other types of marketing (Evans et al., 2021; Leung et al., 2017).

Researchers have found that engagement with brand content on social media can be divided into two phases with the first phase leading to the second phase. The brand drives the engagement in the first phase through regular posts (Obilo et al., 2021). Such information can be in the form of pictures, audio, text, video, or link format with brand pages and groups typically posting daily to drive up the number of participants and participation in the group or on the page. The second phase is more consumer-driven. For instance, consumers can make posts and others respond to the posts consumers. They can also drive up their engagement by opening blogs and accounts designed to rate or discuss products of the brand (Gómez et al., 2019). Overall, it is evident that a key purpose of social media marketing is to drive up brand engagement on social media platforms. Researchers note that brand engagement mediates the correlation between social media marketing and its desired outcomes such as increased purchase intention and brand loyalty (Obilo et al., 2021, Gómez et al., 2019).

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The model by Cheung et al. (2019) informs this study. The researchers identified entertainment, interaction, trendiness, electronic word of mouth, and customization as significant elements of the social media marketing that influence brand knowledge and brand engagement. Cheung et al. (2019), product involvement serves as the moderating variable. Other recent studies (Samsudeen

et al., 2020; Cheung et al., 2020) have confirmed that the model is suitable for assessing the influence of social media marketing on brand engagement.

Entertainment

Entertainment in relation to marketing in general and social media marketing refers to the quality of the marketing content that is enjoyable and playful (Cheung et al., 2019). Entertainment has long been regarded as an effective way to market products and many marketers try to create content that is fun and playful for consumers (Cheung et al., 2020). Social media is primarily a source of interaction and entertainment for most people and marketing content that has a high entertainment value is likely to be well received by consumers on the platform. Entertainment encourages brand interaction and engagement. Studies have shown that people are likely to engage with or share social media content that they find to be entertaining (Schroeder, 2016; Cunningham & Craig, 2019). Entertainment is thus a significant element that determines whether consumers will engage with the brand. In the context of preschool marketing, entertainment can be used as a gateway for interaction and engagement with the brand. Entertaining content can be used to attract parents who can then assess the brand from an academic perspective. The influence of entertainment in social media marketing on brand engagement has been empirically tested. A Facebook survey by Cheung et al. (2019) found that social media marketing-related entertainment has a significant positive influence on brand engagement. A survey of 214 social media users by Samsudeen et al. (2020) and another survey of 433 users of WeChat in China by Cheung et al. (2020) also resulted in a similar finding. These findings provide a basis for the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between entertainment and brand engagement.

Interaction

Interaction has been defined in relation to social media marketing as the communication and involvement among social media users that arises as the users meet, contribute their ideas, and discuss products and brands with other like-minded users on social media platforms (Cheung et al., 2019, Chueng et al., 2020). Social media platforms are primarily designed to facilitate interactions between users (Cunningham & Craig, 2019). It is thus not surprising that interactions can occur around marketing efforts and brands. Social media platforms offer a unique opportunity for two-way interactions and allow users to share their opinions on things freely. Most social media platforms also offer users the opportunity to congregate with other like-minded people in groups or on social media pages that users follow or subscribe to. For instance, brands can have pages or groups where dedicated customers can congregate to receive social media marketing communications. Prior research has shown that interactions on social media increase the level of use of social media and engagement with content on social media (Onofrei et al., 2022, Panagiotopoulos et al., 2015).

Syrdal & Brigs (2018) undertook a qualitative research study that found that social media marketing primarily results from interactions in response to the content posted on social media. Empirical evidence has also affirmed the view that interactions on social media drive brand engagement. The studies by Cheung et al. (2020), Samsudeen et al. (2020), and Cheung et al. (2019) also found that interactions on social media have a significant positive influence on brand engagement on social media. The findings in these studies are the basis of the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant relationship between interaction and brand engagement.

Trendiness

Trendiness broadly refers to the quality of being fashionable (Kryger et al., 2019). It refers to the extent to which something is related to the latest fashion. In relation to social media marketing, trendiness has been defined as the extent to which the marketing communication of brands provides the latest, up-to-date information that is fashionable or paints the brand in a fashionable light in relation to the latest trends (Cheung et al., 2019). Trendiness is an inherent aspect of social media. Consumers increasingly use social media over traditional forms of media because social media is regarded as trendy and fashionable compared to traditional media platforms. Many businesses have adopted social media marketing and built a social media presence because it is regarded as trendy and fashionable with businesses that lack a presence being regarded as old school (Yadav et al., 2018). Researchers note that trendiness is particularly important for younger consumers who often want to identify with the most fashionable brands (Samsudeen et al., 2020; Yadav et al., 2018). Trendiness is also critical in a world where consumption is turning into a form of expression and not merely because of necessity.

The trendiness of social media marketing communication has also been found to drive brand engagement. Cheung et al. (2020) noted trendiness enhances engagement because consumers want to be readily identified with the latest best brands. Cheung et al. (2020) confirmed the findings in empirical research. The empirical study of 433 WeChat users found a positive and statistically significant relationship between social media interactions related to social media marketing and consumer brand engagement on the platform. The studies by Samsudeen et al. (2020) and Cheung et al. (2019) all also found that trendiness has a significant positive influence on brand engagement on social media. These findings are the basis for the third hypothesis of this study:

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant relationship between trendiness and brand engagement.

Customization

Customization generally refers to the act of modifying something to make it more suitable for a particular person or task (Puzakova et al., 2013). Social media marketing refers to the act of providing marketing information that is relevant and suitable to individual consumers (Cheung et al., 2019). Customization is about meeting the preferences of individuals. It makes it easier for individual consumers to search for relevant information and to make use of the information. Researchers contend that the customizations of marketing information and products make consumers feel valued and build trust in the minds of consumers (Cheung et al., 2019; Cheung et al., 2020). Customization shows that the brand cares about specific consumers or specific groups of consumers. A relevant example of customization of marketing information on social media is direct responses to the queries of consumers on the platform. This direct engagement provides information that is highly relevant to the consumers.

Research has shown that the customization of marketing information increases brand engagement (Cheung et al., 2019; Samsudeen et al., 2020; Berger). These empirical research studies all found that customization has a positive and statistically significant influence on brand

engagement on social media platforms. Liu et al. (2021) found that customization is particularly important for luxury products that are used by consumers as a status symbol or personal statement. The researchers found that a failure to personalize information and products can lead to the loss of customers. These findings are the basis for the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant relationship between customization and brand engagement.

Electronic Word of Mouth

Word of mouth generally refers to the passage of information through oral communication (Berger, 2014). In marketing, the term has been used to refer to the situation where a consumer's or customer's interest in a product, service, or brand is reflected in their dialogues while interacting with other people (Huete-Alcocer, 2017). Word of mouth has long been regarded as one of the most powerful forms of marketing. It involves customers talking to their loved ones and other contacts about products, services, and brands and is highly effective because it is organic and is not viewed as coming from the business itself which has a vested interest in increasing its sales. The power of word-of-mouth marketing is seen in the survey by Neilsen (31) which found that 92% of people trust the recommendations of family and friends over all other forms of advertising. In recent years, as digital marketing and social media use has become more widespread, a new iteration or word of mouth marketing, electronic word-of-mouth marketing (electronic word of mouth) has emerged. Electronic word of mouth has been defined as "any positive or negative statement made by potential, actual, or former customers about a product or company, which is made available to a multitude of people and institutions via the Internet" (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2014 pg. 39).

Electronic word of mouth has a broader scope than typical word of mouth in that it often involves strangers assessing the sentiments of other consumers. The most widely noted form of electronic word of mouth is product reviews on online stores and e-commerce websites. Product reviews are critical as they provide information to other consumers on the extent to which products align with the expectations of consumers. Studies have shown that many e-commerce consumers trust product reviews by other consumers who have used the products over professional reviews (Wang et al., 2015). Many consumers read through product reviews before making purchases in online stores. Consumers have also shown a strong preference for stores where consumer reviews are allowed over those where there are no reviews. Electronic word of mouth goes beyond formalized consumer reviews.

Empirical research evidence supports the view that electronic word of mouth has a significant positive effect on brand engagement. A survey of 712 social media users in India by Srivastava & Sivaramakrishnan (2018) found that increased exposure to electronic word of mouth has a positive and statistically significant effect on brand engagement in the specific product categories that were assessed. Notably, the study also found that electronic word of mouth has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction with those who are exposed to positive electronic word of mouth related to a purchased product being more likely to report higher levels of satisfaction with the product. Other empirical research studies have also found a positive and statistically significant correlation between the electronic word of mouth and brand engagement (Cheung et al., 2019; Samsudeen et al., 2020; Cheung et al., 2020). The findings of these studies provide a basis for the final hypothesis of this research study:

Hypothesis 5: There is a significant relationship between electronic word of mouth and brand engagement.

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

The theory that underpins this study is the relationship marketing theory by Berry (1983) who created the COBRA model. The theory holds that creating unique relationships is the basis for effective marketing which explains why creating brand engagement is strongly desired. The COBRA model is used to understand behavioural engagement with brands on social media. According to the theory, brand engagement on social media is best understood by using three dimensions: consumption, contribution, and creation (Schivinski et al., 2016). The model shows an escalating form of brand engagement.

It is relevant for this study because it highlights how brand engagement can be related to social media marketing. Consumption of brand-related content arises mostly because of social media marketing by brands. Factors such as customizations and trendiness increase the chances of brand-related media being consumed while factors such as entertainment and interaction increase the chances of contribution. Content creation can be viewed as electronic word of mouth which encourages brand engagement. The model proposed by Cheung et al. (2019) is relevant because the social media marketing elements that serve as the independent variables for this study are drawn from the model. The Cheung et al. (2019) model highlights the elements of the social media marketing that affect brand engagement. It shows that there are five primary elements that have a significant impact on consumer brand engagement: entertainment, interactions, customizations, electronic word of mouth, and trendiness. It is relevant for this project since these are the elements that will be tested. While the elements have been tested in other contexts, there is a need to test them in the context of brand engagement for preschools in Malaysia. The two models together are thus appropriate for this study as they both show how social media marketing can influence brand engagement on social media. The framework below is adapted from the Cheung et al. (2019) model:

Figure 2.2: Conceptual framework for this study (adapted from Cheung et al. (2019)).

METHODOLOGY

STUDY DESIGN and SAMPLES

The correlational cross-sectional research design was used in this study. This design is usually used together with the quantitative research methodology. The quantitative methodology was preferred because it results in findings that have higher validity and reliability (Queirós et al., 2017). The descriptive cross-sectional design was suitable because the intention of the study was not to show causality but to show a correlation between the variables. The descriptive design is typically used where a study only intends to show a correlation rather than a cause-and-effect relationship (Siedlecki, 2020). The samples of this study were drawn from millennial parents from the District of Petaling, Selangor, Malaysia. Parents are an appropriate population because they are the primary clientele of preschools. The parents who were following their children's (age 4-6 years) school accounts on social media platforms (WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram) formed the target population of this study. The sample size for this study was estimated based on the method proposed by Leblanc & Fitzgerald (2000) who recommended a minimum of 30 respondents for every predictor variable in a study. Based on this recommendation, the minimum suitable sample size for this study was 150 participants as there are five predictor variables in this study. A sample size of 200 pre-schools parents was deemed suitable for the study as it is above the recommended minimum. Five schools were selected at random from each of the four mukims in the District of Petaling and ten teachers were selected at random from each of the 20 schools included in the study. All respondents answered an online survey via Google Form.

INSTRUMENTS AND MEASUREMENTS

A self-administered structured questionnaire was used for data collection in this study. The questionnaire had four items for social media marketing-related entertainment, five items for social media marketing-related customization, four items for social media marketing-related interaction, three items for social media marketing-related electronic word of mouth and three items for social media marketing-related trendiness. All the items for these independent variables were adapted from the study by Kim & Ko (2010). There were ten items on consumer brand engagement (the dependent variable). The items were adapted from the studies by Leckie et al. (2016), Longaro et al. (2018), and Godey et al. (2016). The independent variables were operationalized based on the study by Cheung et al. (2019) while the dependent variable was operationalized based on the study by Cheung et al. (2020). A seven-point Likert agreement scale was used to measure the items on the variables of the study.

RESEARCH PROCEDURES

A pilot study of 30 respondents was undertaken to assess the feasibility of the study prior to the actual study. Participants in the pilot study were not included in the actual study. Participant recruitment occurred after the pilot study had been successfully undertaken and the reliability of the questionnaire was assessed based on the findings of the pilot study. Questionnaires were then sent out either via WhatsApp or email depending on the individual preference of each respondent. The respondents were given a maximum of 24 hours to complete and send back the questionnaire. 190 respondents sent back the questionnaire within the allocated time frame. However, the remaining ten respondents were able to send back the filled-out questionnaire on follow-up. Descriptive statistical analysis was performed to understand the respondents' demographic characteristics. Reliability and normality were also been assessed. Pearson's correlation coefficient analysis (with significance set at $r = +/- 0.1$) and linear regression analysis (with significance set at $p = 0.05$) were used to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Characteristics

Most respondents were male (56.5%), married (49%), and Muslim (60%). The two biggest age groupings of respondents in this survey are those between the ages of 18 and 25 years (61 percent) and those between the ages of 26 and 35 years (30 percent). Most people (62%) were earning less than RM5, 000, with only 31.5% of respondents earning between RM5, 001 and RM15, 000. The least proportion of respondents (1.5%) were earning above RM25, 001. Most respondents (49%) had a Diploma education, 17.5% had a foundation education, 16% had a bachelor's degree education, 11% had a High School education and 6.5% had a master's degree education.

Reliability Analysis

Table 1. Reliability analysis

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Conclusion
Entertainment	0.845	4	Reliable
Customizations	0.912	5	Reliable
Interaction	0.729	4	Reliable
Trendiness	0.803	3	Reliable
Electronic Word of Mouth (electronic word of mouth)	0.842	3	Reliable
Brand Engagement	0.953	10	Reliable

According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), reliability values less than 0.60 are considered suboptimal, those between 0.70 and 0.80 are considered conventional, and those greater than 0.80 are considered excellent. The closer Cronbach's alpha is to one, the more reliable the internal consistency. Based on the result in Table 1, the Cronbach alpha coefficients for the dependent variable, Brand engagement, and the independent variables, Entertainment, Customization, Interaction, Trendiness, and Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) are 0.93, 0.845, 0.912, 0.729, 0.803, and 0.953. The Cronbach alpha coefficients for all dependent and independent variables are considered acceptable, indicating that the items have a high degree of internal consistency.

Normality Testing

Normality analysis was undertaken using Kurtosis and Skewness measures for the data collected.

Table 2. Normality analysis

	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Entertainment	-.864	.172	-.051	.342
Customization	-.371	.172	-.565	.342
Interaction	-.266	.172	-.191	.342
Trendiness	-.399	.172	-.787	.342
Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM)	-.627	.172	-.129	.342
Brand Engagement	-.955	.172	1.291	.342

This study used the statistical methods of skewness and kurtosis to determine normality. Hair et al. (2010) and Bryne (2010) argued that data is normal if skewness falls between -2 to +2 and kurtosis is between -7 to +7. Based on the result of table 2, the skewness and the kurtosis for the dependent variable and independent variables fall between -0.955 to -0.266 and -0.787 to 1.291. The skewness and kurtosis values of the independent and dependent variables are within these ranges. It can conclude that the data is normally distributed.

Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis examination was used in this study, to test the relationship between trendiness, entertainment, interactions, electronic word of mouth, customization, and brand engagement among preschool parents in Malaysia.

Table 3. Pearson Correlation Analysis

		Entertainment	Customizations	Interaction	Trendiness	Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM)	Brand Engagement
Entertainment	Pearson Correlation	1	.760*	.440*	.574*	.480*	.309*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
Customization	Pearson Correlation	.760*	1	.394*	.545*	.587*	.425*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
Interaction	Pearson Correlation	.440*	.394*	1	.752*	.589*	.548*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
Trendiness	Pearson Correlation	.574*	.545*	.752*	1	.648*	.456*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM)	Pearson Correlation	.480*	.587*	.589*	.648*	1	.451*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
Consumer Brand Engagement	Pearson Correlation	.309*	.425*	.548*	.456*	.451*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	200	200	200	200	200	200
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							

Based on the result in table 3, the coefficient of correlation r between brand engagement and all independent variables: Entertainment is (0.309), Customization is (0.425), Interaction is (0.548), Trendiness is (0.456) and Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM) is (0.451). The result showed the strength of the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables is positively moderate.

Linear Regression Analysis

Linear regression analysis was conducted to conceptualize the influence of social media marketing (trendiness, entertainment, interactions, electronic word of mouth, and customization) on brand engagement among preschool parents in Malaysia.

Table 4. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.721	.520	.508
a. Predictors: (Constant), Electronic Word of Mouth (electronic word of mouth), Entertainment, Interaction, Customization, Trendiness			

Based on the result in table 4, the R-squared value was found to be 0.52. This finding implies 52% variation in brand engagement can be explained by all the independent variables (trendiness, entertainment, interactions, electronic word of mouth, and customization).

Table 5 ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	111.876	5	22.375	22.789	.000 ^b
	Residual	190.479	194	.982		
	Total	302.355	199			
a. Dependent Variable: Brand Engagement						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Electronic Word of Mouth (electronic word of mouth), Entertainment, Interaction, Customization, Trendiness						

Based on the result in table 5, at the 95 percent confidence level, the ANOVA results indicate an F-value of 22.789 and a p-value of 0.000 which implies that the model of trendiness, entertainment, interactions, electronic word of mouth, and customization dimensions in predicting consumer brand engagement is significant.

Table 5. Model parameters (BE):

Source	Value	Standard error	t	Pr > t	Lower bound (95%)	Upper bound (95%)
Intercept	1.685	0.411	4.102	< 0.0001	0.875	2.495

ETN	-0.158	0.090	-1.745	0.083	-0.336	0.021
CUST	0.322	0.109	2.961	0.003	0.107	0.536
INT	0.419	0.086	4.850	< 0.0001	0.248	0.589
TREND	0.017	0.092	0.181	0.857	-0.165	0.198
eWOM	0.101	0.093	1.093	0.276	-0.082	0.284

The following hypotheses were tested:

H1: There is a significant relationship between entertainment and brand engagement.

H2: There is a significant relationship between customization and brand engagement.

H3: There is a significant relationship between interaction and brand engagement.

H4: There is a significant relationship between trendiness and brand engagement.

H5: There is a significant relationship between electronic word of mouth and brand engagement.

The regression coefficient and the P-value for entertainment are (B1=-0.158, p-value=0.083), trendiness (B4=0.017, p-value=0.857) and electronic word of mouth (B5=0.101, p-value=0.276). This indicates that the relationship between entertainment and brand engagement; between trendiness and brand engagement; and between the electronic word of mouth and brand engagement are not significant. While the regression coefficient and the P-value for customization are (B2=0.322, 0.003), and interaction (B3=0.419, p-value= < 0.0001). This result indicates that the relationship between customization and brand engagement and interaction and brand engagement are significant. From the above result, it was concluded that H2 and H3 are supported. Whereas H1, H4 and H5 are not supported.

CONCLUSION

The study aimed at examining the effects of social media marketing on brand engagement in preschools in the Petaling District. All five objectives of the study as outlined were achieved during the research. The findings of the study confirmed that the relationship between customization and brand engagement is positive and significant. The relationship between interaction and brand engagement is also confirmed to be positive and significant. The independent variables of entertainment, trendiness and electronic word of mouth are not significant to brand engagement among the preschool parent.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study highlighted why brand engagement is essential for preschoolers and the factors influencing brand engagement with social media content. The preschool education landscape in the country has become increasingly competitive in the last few decades. The results obtained will be essential for parents' teachers and the management of the preschool institution in

developing the marketing strategy. It will enable them to understand how to engage social media in the education sector effectively to get more clients. The study will allow preschools to increase their competitiveness by increasing brand engagement with their consumers, in this case, the parents. Understanding the factors that influence consumer brand engagement helps preschools to increase the number of students and develop the best marketing strategies to attract millennial parents. The study is also beneficial to parents of preschoolers to gauge preschools and select the best ones based on the preschool's social media presence mainly because they get their information from social media which strongly influences their consumer behaviour.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study consisted only of a small population in one of the districts in Malaysia. The participants chosen were only preschool-going children in the district. The population sample comprised more male parents than their female counterparts, yet in most cases, it's the female parents who interact with their school-going kids at home after school. The research was based only on preschool children instead of focusing on all school-going children. Additionally, parents do not use social media platforms like WhatsApp and Facebook and were not included in the study meaning that generalizations cannot be made about them.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In future studies, a larger population can be used to avoid generalizations of the results. To get more effective results, the participants can be mixed up so that the responses obtained include teachers' learners and parents of preschool and other grades. Such a diverse population can lead to mixed results during the study. An equal number of male and female parents should be used to avoid biases. Female parents should be more than their male counterparts in case of a disparity as they are primarily involved with taking care of their kids. Future research can focus on the effect of social media on all school-going children to focus on the areas to improve in schooling activities, especially in the lower classes. Research can be carried out to include all those parents without social media accounts by filling in hard-copy questionnaires.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection, analysis, writing and revising the manuscript.

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